

Disease resistance

Varietal resistance to stem rot (SR) and bacterial blight (BB)

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SR, caused by *Sclerotium oryzae*, and BB, caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, are major rice diseases in Haryana. We evaluated 177 early- to mid-duration rices for their reaction to those diseases at HAURRS in 1983-84.

Each entry was planted in 2-m rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Plants were clip inoculated with a BB suspension at maximum tillering and scored for resistance using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. SR screening was in field plots and also in the laboratory. In the laboratory, cut stem pieces were wound-inoculated with a small piece of agar-cultured *S. oryzae*. The inoculated stems were kept in standing position with a test tube rack in a tray with 2.5 cm of water. They were covered with plastic bags to retain high moisture and incubated at 28-30°C. Lesion length was measured 10 d after inoculation. Entries with lesions less than 10 mm long were

Rices with SR and BB resistance, Haryana, India.

Entry	Parentage	Reaction ^a to		
		SR		BB
		Field	Laboratory	
HAU118-87	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	R	R	R
HAU118-110	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	R	R	R
HAU118-111	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	R	R	R
BR51-282-8	IR20/IR5-114-3-1	R	R	R
IR42	IR1561-228//4*IR24/O. nivara///CR 94-13	R	R	R
IR2588-34-5-6	IR1544-238-2-3/IR1529-680-3	R	R	R
IR2681-90-4	CR94///IR20 ³ /O. nivara//IR1541-102-6	R	R	MR
HAU118-163	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	MR	MR	R
HAU118-195	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	MR	MR	R
HAU118-752	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	MR	MR	R
HAU118-754	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	MR	MR	R
HAU118-755	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	MR	MR	R
IR54	Nam Sagui 19/IR2071-88// IR2061-214-3-6-20	MR	MR	R

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

considered resistant; those with 10-30 mm lesions, moderately resistant; and those with more than 30 mm, susceptible.

Disease pressure was high for SR (location severity index [LSI] 6.79 in the field and 6.05 in the laboratory), and

moderate (LSI 3.12) for BB. Of the entries tested, 125 showed resistance to BB, 19 to field SR, and 44 to laboratory SR. Six entries were resistant to both BB and SR (see table) and had good agronomic traits. □

Evaluation of hill rice germplasm for leaf blast (BI) resistance

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BI is a serious constraint to rice production in hilly regions. We evaluated 1,271 cultivars from the hill area of Uttar Pradesh for BI resistance under artificial epiphytotic conditions at the VLHA experimental farm at Hawalbagh (1,250 mean sea level).

Cultivars were planted in the Uniform Blast Nursery pattern. VL8 was the resistant check and Ch 1039 and HR12 were the susceptible checks. Although the initial inoculum was sufficient to start

Reaction of 1,271 cultivars to B1 at 30, 40, and 57 DAS, Almora, India.

SES score	30 DAS		40 DAS		57 DAS	
	Cultivar nos.	Infection (%)	Cultivar nos.	Infection (%)	Cultivar nos.	Infection (%)
0	20	1.6	1	0.1	0	0
1	33	2.6	0	0.0	0	0
2	101	7.9	8	0.6	0	0
3	430	41.7	27	2.1	0	0
4	587	46.2	633	49.8	17	1.3
5	0	—	573	45.1	132	10.4
6	0	—	28	2.2	309	24.3
7	0	—	1	0.1	583	45.9
8	0	—	0	—	184	14.5
9	0	—	0	—	46	3.6

infection, for heavy disease pressure we prepared a fresh conidial suspension from infected leaves and sprayed it on 15-d-old

seedlings. The nursery was planted on 3 Jul 1982 and BI incidence was recorded 30, 40, and 57 d after sowing (DAS). In